

Supporting Information

Beyond the catalyst: Role of the cell configuration, electrolyte concentration and ionomer content on the performance of Cu based CO₂ electrolyzers.

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Sections Overview

S.1 Electrochemical Data

Figure S 1 Catholyte-flow chronoamperometry data measured at -1.6V Vs Ag/AgCl a) without Nafion, b) with 9% Nafion

Figure S 2 H-cell chronoamperometry data measured at -1.6V Vs Ag/AgCl a) without Nafion, b) with 9% Nafion

SI Note 1: Contact angle data

Nafion %	Contact Angle (°)
0% Nafion	0°
0.3% Nafion	30°
5% Nafion	157°
9% Nafion	158°
13% Nafion	145°

SI Note 2: X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)

The X-ray absorption spectroscopy data fitting was done by specifying constraints for the peak position, fwhm, and line shape and using the auto fit components option of CasaXPS.

Correction with respect to adventitious carbon (284.5 eV) was carried out for all samples. The list of peaks and the constraints for the X-ray measurements are mentioned in the following table. The fitting parameters were taken from the study by Biesinger et.al.,^{1,2}

Name	CuO (B)	CuO	CuO	CuO			
Line Shape	GL(30)	GL(30)	GL(30)	GL(30)			
Area constraint	B	B * 1,53	B * 1,19	B* 0,115			
fwhm constraint	3,67 - 3,69	2,03 - 2,05	4,65 - 4,67	2,21 - 2,23			
Position Constraint	919,8 - 920 (B)	B - 2,06	B - 5,7	B - 8,55			
Name	Cu(OH)2 (F)	Cu(OH)2	Cu(OH)2				
Line Shape	GL(30)	GL(30)	GL(30)				
Area constraint	F	F * 6,9	F * 2,1				
fwhm constraint	3,31 - 3,33	4,05 - 4,07	4,46 - 4,48				
Position Constraint	920 - 920,2 (F)	F - 3,59	F - 8,18				
Name	Cu2O (I)	Cu2O	Cu2O	Cu2O			
Line Shape	GL(30)	GL(30)	GL(30)	GL(30)			
Area constraint	I	I * 11	I * 4,6	I * 3,4			
fwhm constraint	2,1 - 2,3	4 - 4,02	1,56 - 1,58	4 - 4,2			
Position Constraint	921,6 - 921,8 (I)	I - 3,79	I - 4,88	I - 8,55			
Name	Cu (M)	Cu	Cu	Cu	Cu	Cu	Cu
Line Shape	GL(30)	GL(30)	GL(30)	GL(30)	GL(30)	GL(30)	GL(30)
Area constraint	M	M * 0,76	M * 1,76	M * 2,23	M * 0,46	M * 1,38	M * 0,076
fwhm constraint	1,27 - 1,29	1 - 1,2	0,74 - 0,94	2,31 - 2,33	1 - 1,2	2,77 - 2,79	1,41 - 1,43
Position Constraint	921,2 - 921,4 (M)	M - 1,65	M - 2,71	M - 3,26	M - 5,15	M - 7,09	M - 10,41

Additional XPS data

Figure S 3 Cu LMM Auger spectra for a) catholyte-flow electrolyzers with and without Nafion., b) zero-gap electrolyzers with and without Nafion. The effect of electrolyte concentration was also investigated. The complete experimental conditions are given in the figure inset.

References

1. Biesinger, M. C. Advanced analysis of copper X-ray photoelectron spectra. *Surf. Interface Anal.* **49**, 1325–1334 (2017).
2. Biesinger, M. C., Lau, L. W. M., Gerson, A. R. & Smart, R. St. C. Resolving surface chemical states in XPS analysis of first row transition metals, oxides and hydroxides: Sc, Ti, V, Cu and Zn. *Appl Surf Sci* **257**, 887–898 (2010).